

**CDB / CARICOM / OECS Model
Learning Recovery and Enhancement
Programme for Caribbean Schools**

Let's REAP!

Roadmap for Ministries

<https://lreap.info>

**Organisation of
Eastern Caribbean States**

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All **Let's REAP!** materials are available from all partner organisations: www.caribank.org/letitrip, caricom.org/letitrip and oecs.int/letitrip, as well as at letitrip.info.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AFL	Assessment for Learning
CARICOM	Caribbean Community
CDB	Caribbean Development Bank
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019 caused by SARS-CoV-2
EdTech	Educational technology
EDMU	OECS Education Development Management Unit
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
Let's REAP!	Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme (L-R-EA-P)
MoE	Ministry of Education
OECS	Organization of Eastern Caribbean States
OER	Open educational resources
PD	Professional Development
RBMEF	Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework
SPED	Special education and disability
TPD	Teacher professional development

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

The COVID-19 pandemic brought significant disruption to the education systems of CARICOM *member states* and other parts of the region, exacerbating existing stresses on the education system. This further widened the education gaps between high-performing and low-performing students, particularly for already disadvantaged learners. Disadvantaged learners include learners of low socio-economic status and those that have special education needs or a disability (SPED).

A learning recovery programme (**Let's REAP!**) was designed to help students meet learning outcomes commensurate with their grade. To achieve this, a multi-pronged approach must be taken, supporting both teachers and learners. As a senior OECS representative suggested that

*“[the **Let's REAP!** is] an intervention for the teacher, as much as it is an intervention for the child.”*

There are also broader implications for parents, as well as organisations in the wider community. The **Let's REAP!** will be implemented differently across each participating *Member State*. Still, there are common areas that all participating countries need to consider maximising the effectiveness of their interventions.

This concept note and the available implementation guidance documentation (see below) offer overall implementation guidance. However, importantly, the materials also suggest an indicative timeline and budget for implementing each **Let's REAP!** component, highlighting critical tasks and responsibilities.

2. Planning and preparation

Some key points should be noted when planning the implementation of the **Let's REAP!**:

The Let's REAP! needs to be context-specific

The programme was not designed as a 'model' or 'blueprint', not a 'one-size-fits-all' intervention. Careful thought needs to be given to the balance of emphasis given to the programme's different components in each school and each territory. Each school will need to adapt the programme to suit the realities of their context. The role of the MoE is to support schools during this process.

The programme is also focused on improvement, not only recovery

Clearly 'recovery' and 'remediation' is important. However, we need to recognise that even before the pandemic there were deep inequities as well as dissatisfaction with learning outcomes in the Caribbean. The programme is ultimately an improvement programme. The first step in this improvement is to help mitigate the impact of the pandemic. However, this is only the first step. The programme provides a framework for recovery and improvement, to be executed over the years to come. The MoE should ensure that measures are in place to support continuity of school improvement. The guide makes suggestions about monitoring frameworks which will be useful in that process.

There are no 'selection criteria' for schools

Given that **Let's REAP!** ultimately focuses on improvement, we note that the programme is designed to be implemented in all schools, primary and secondary. Different schools in different areas will have been affected differently by the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and other events in different ways. However, all schools can benefit from the programme. The MoE needs to make sure that all schools participate in the recovery process so that they could benefit from overall improvement in learning.

Let's REAP! does not target specific grades

The programme is not just intended for specific grades (e.g., for primary grades or grades where students change schools) — **Let's REAP!** is there to support all students. In particular, **Let's REAP!** will ensure that all students achieve specific skills. For example, any primary student who does not have the required skills in literacy and numeracy needs to be able to access recovery needs. This means that

2. Planning and preparation

evaluating *all* primary students and identifying those most in need of intervention is a vital part of both the planning and the monitoring aspects of the programme.

Management, monitoring, communication

Management oversight, monitoring and communication are critical to the success of **Let's REAP!** implementation, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of its impact. Component 2 specifically focuses on management. Alongside activities, The [Implementation Planning Tool](#) contains suggested monitoring tools as well as results-based monitoring and evaluation frameworks.

Make sure all teachers participate

It is critical that all teachers participate. If a teacher does not participate, it means that the children and young people in their care will not benefit from **Let's REAP!** as much as they could be. All teachers may not want to participate immediately, they can engage through teacher professional development, which should be on the timetable. Encourage schools to include the TPD on the timetable so that it is easier for teachers to participate.

The unit of transformation is the school

There is a lot of evidence on school improvement. An important insight is that teaching and learning is not just dependent on good teachers. A large part of successful learning depends on the environment in school — how teachers engage with each other, what environment the principal creates, and so forth. We sometimes say that the 'unit of transformation is the school'. Therefore, supporting principals to create communities of practice with teachers at their school, is extremely important. Teachers will be required to meet at least one a week in groups of up to 20.

2.1. The management and implementation team

Let's REAP! implementation management will need strong coordination at **all levels**, but **leadership** needs to come at a **national level**. We therefore recommend that the MoE constitute a **national Let's REAP! management and implementation team**. The **Let's REAP!** Management and Implementation Team should consist of teachers from each school district/zone. If possible, include a member of the local community as well. The team should oversee, monitor, and, where necessary, intervene in the implementation of the **Let's REAP!**'s components in each territory. At the school level, ensure that principals enlist at least 2 teachers at their school to

2. Planning and preparation

support them in the implementation of the learning recovery program. The selected teachers will form the school-based implementation team. The MoE **management and implementation team** should work closely with the school-based implementation team to monitor the effective execution of the **Let's REAP!** Although the implementation of the **Let's REAP!** is country-specific, it is also a regional programme taking place across several participating *member states*, with the potential for several others to join in future. The **Let's REAP!** management and implementation team should meet weekly with coordinators in other participating *member states* to coordinate efforts and share practice advice across the region.

2.2. Monitoring and Reporting Plan

Oversight and communication will be key to the success of **Let's REAP!** implementation, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of its impact. A Monitoring and Reporting Plan should be agreed with the MoE and stakeholders of each country's **Let's REAP!** Management and Implementation Team. The [Implementation Planning Tool](#) contains indicative activity plans, as well as a suggested results-based monitoring and evaluation framework addressing each activity.

2.3. Prioritising and planning implementation

The [Implementation Planning Tool](#) is a flexible tool that is intended to allow planning of the **Let's REAP!** components to be tailored to be specific to the context of the *member state* implementing it.

The [Implementation Planning Tool](#) should be used as follows:

- Each of the programme's nine components is given its own tab within the Tool. Review each of the tabs labelled Component 1 to Component 9 and prioritise the more relevant activities to you. To prioritise the activities, review the indicative timeline for the implementation of each activity and indicate the appropriate months for implementation. Note that crucial recommended activities are highlighted in bold.
- Once the activities to be implemented have been decided upon, enter them into the blank tab entitled 'Your Gantt chart' by copying and pasting them.

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Adjust or amend the timelines as necessary by entering or deleting the letter 'x' under each relevant month.

- Identify the specific actions to take, the required staff effort, the necessary resources, and the financial cost of each activity in columns F-I. Some indicative suggestions have been provided, but these should be confirmed in discussion with the relevant stakeholders and the **Let's REAP!** implementation and management team in each participating state. There is also a timeline that countries may use to prioritise and execute various components of the **Let's REAP!**.
- Consult the tab entitled 'RBMEF' to view an indicative results-based monitoring and evaluation framework, with suggested outputs and indicators for each activity. These indicators can form the basis of a Monitoring and Reporting Plan, to be agreed with the MoE of each member state.

3. Implementation

3. Implementation

Given the small-scale nature of the ARP OECS trialling so far, several recommendations are made here to support the successful scaling of **Let's REAP!** through the other CARICOM *member states*. These recommendations should be considered when reviewing activities in the [Implementation Planning Tool](#).

Let's REAP! is made up of nine components, which can be prioritized by each *member state* based on context needs. The components work at the regional, nation and school level to support the overall success of the recovery programme across the regions and individual schools.

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Figure 1. The design of **Let's REAP!**. The programme is designed for systemic integration across four locations (regional, national, schools, community) with nine components of activity.

3.1. Leadership and accountability

Leadership occurs on three levels: regional, national and school level. At the regional level, the CDB, CARICOM and OECS empower, guide and finance the **Let's REAP!**. Thus, the MoE follows guidance from regional institutions listed above. At the national level, the MoE directs the implementation process in ways that facilitate the ease of implementation at the school level. The MoE will participate in cross-country and cross-sector communities of practice to facilitate sharing of best practice and standardization across the region. Collaboration at the regional level will also help address issues of equity through resource sharing and management. At every level, the MoE supports, monitors and evaluates the implementation of the **Let's REAP!** and also receives support for regional institutions. The MoE must ensure that proper frameworks are in place to monitor and evaluate **Let's REAP!** implementation.

For Ministries of Education, the most urgent actions are to

1. Use the overall guidance from CARICOM to customise your recovery programme;
2. Participate in cross-country and cross-sector activities;
3. Develop a framework to monitor and support implementation programme in your country.

You should

1. Submit the national recovery programme to **Let's REAP!** team at the regional level;
2. Develop database of networks for cross-country and cross-sector collaborations.

3.1.1. Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C1L2.1	Implement leadership programme for principals; adapt programme as necessary	Provide schools with the LfL and put in place measures to evaluate and monitor programme effectiveness
C1L2.2	Monitor & Evaluate progress	Develop monitoring and evaluation frameworks to track principals' progress. Set up a schedule with guidance for them to submit progress and evidence of it. Report results to regional orgs.
C1L2.3	Participate in regional Let's REAP! team	Participation in Regional Let's REAP! team; participation in leadership programme for MoEs.
C1L2.4	Student participation	Collaborate with the National Youth Council to adapt guidance on student involvement to encourage student participation at all levels.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.2. Management and communication

Education decision-makers in the Caribbean face the challenge of managing a diverse learning community: many languages, varied socioeconomic contexts and differential learning levels within and between states. A lack of dynamic data and low implementation capacity exacerbates the challenge of identifying and addressing barriers to equitable, quality and relevant education. This issue contributes to the ineffective allocation of resources, with those in rural communities facing the biggest obstacles to education opportunities.

This situation points to a need for strengthened system's management. To accomplish this, the following actions are recommended.

1. Data for decision-making;
2. GIS for education planning;
3. Embedded agile delivery.

Data for decision-making requires school leaders to collect, relay and use dynamic school-level data for overall school and academic improvement. It also mandates that school leaders receive training in collecting disaggregated data on vulnerable groups (e.g., SPED, gender, non-native speakers). This is particularly significant as boys tend to underperform and drop out, while SPED students are severely marginalized in terms of customising education to respond to their needs. Importantly, a database should be developed to consolidate all data to monitor access, equity, quality and relevance across the schools. Finally, diagnostic report cards and dashboards will be developed with decision-makers to monitor and communicate results of diagnostic tests, but also to improve delivery and administration of diagnostic tests to all categories of students.

GIS for education planning will facilitate the use of geospatial data to determine the nature of support specific communities need, leading to efficient and equitable resource allocation. In addition, it will inform a more equitable allocation of teachers in each island while accounting for the preferences of individual instructors. In the end, it will contribute to overall improvement in education by tackling one community at a time.

Embedded agile delivery means that decision-makers will receive regular training

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to apply an agile delivery approach to drive change across the sector. Agile development involves an iterative and adaptable approach with planned points to assess if and how a product or service can better meet the needs of users and adapt to the context. Decision-makers will learn to start small and incrementally develop services to minimise risk before going to scale.

3.2.1. Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C2L1.2	System for data collection	Develop a system to guide school leaders in data collection. The system should facilitate relaying of information and use of dynamic school-level data for overall school and academic improvement. Implement a system that will facilitate collection of geospatial data to determine schools most in need and guide teacher and resource allocation. Training modules to be developed including collecting disaggregated data on vulnerable groups (e.g., SPED, gender, non-native speakers).
C2L2.1	Training	Tailor data collection modules developed regionally to the local contexts. Schedule modules as part of the training for principals.
C2L2.1	Collaborate with National Youth Council (NYC)	Meet with NYC to discuss how student data will be used in Let's REAP! and overall school improvement. Also, discuss Let's REAP! implementation plan.
C2L2.1	Caribbean Education Hub — A registry for programmes, evidence and resources.	Ministries provide information for the Caribbean Education Hub.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.3. Regional and national partnerships

Strategic partners play vital roles in equipping schools to close learning gaps. The implementation document guides auditing, evaluating and establishing new partners and retaining relevant partnerships. The guide encourages school administrators to ensure that school goals, values and interests are mutual so that effective partnerships can be formed.

Record keeping frameworks are recommended to allow for monitoring relationships, contributions and arising needs. This effectively enables schools to maintain strategic relationships with private and public sector officials who can contribute tangibly in helping schools close learning gaps.

3.3.1. Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C3L2.1	Desk-based research and partnership audit	<p>Undertake desk-based review of all the current actors in the field and create or update a database with relevant information about their operations.</p> <p>The evaluation could be supported by local consultants to assess partnerships.</p> <p>Carry out an audit of all existing partnerships to determine the state of those existing partnerships</p>
C3L2.2	Partnership modelling	Based on the information gathered, review partnership models as they are best suited for (primary and secondary) learners. Some partnership models to be explored include brokering, and providing support, and establishing networks.
C3L2.3	Establish new partnerships	Establish new partnerships with relevant actors and incorporate them into monitoring frameworks as necessary. Partnerships need to be built with organisations that can support students with SPED needs.
C3L2.4	Record keeping	Maintain and update records of partnerships, as well as renewed searches to identify new potential partners
C3L2.5	Partner/Resource Coordination	Establish a team with sole responsibility of coordinating partner contributions. Their role should include synthesising resources to avoid duplication. This will enable better allocation of partner resources and efforts

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.4. Facilitate teacher professional development

The **Let's REAP!** programme was designed with flexibility around the implementation of its components. However, support to teachers in the form of teacher professional development (TPD) sessions should be considered an activity that is central to the programme's success. Implementing TPD is time-intensive and requires both planning and enthusiasm.

However, school-based practice-focused TPD has important benefits:

- TPD can be very effective in improving learning outcomes;
- TPD offers opportunities for peer support.

As much as possible, the TPD should incorporate the range of suggestions below to ensure the success of the **Let's REAP!**

3.4.1. Ensure facilitators are aware of the sessions' technology requirements

The TPD programme can take place face-to-face (in schools). It can also take place virtually, using the preferred video conferencing software. If the programme takes place virtually, it is important that the appropriate technology provisions are made.

Just like teachers preparing for blended learning for students, facilitators need to be aware of the technological requirements necessary to ensure the smooth and time-efficient flow of the sessions. This is particularly important when sharing external media such as videos and presentations and includes:

- Being aware of the settings for sharing video/audio during calls;
- Remembering to make closed captioning visible for those unable to hear audio; and
- Running through third-party media beforehand to be able to start from identified bookmarks.

Technology can be challenging to use; however, adequate preparation ahead of each session ensures that the maximum time can be dedicated to achieving the outcomes of each session and that participants remain engaged.

3.4.2. TPD must fit with teaching schedules

In some participating states, time is already allocated for regular TPD sessions (such as INSET days or abbreviated schooldays). Implementation of TPD activities should be scheduled to minimise interference with the already difficult task of teaching in the new normal of the blended learning environment. Keeping teachers onside and engaged with the content is important to ensuring the effectiveness of TPD activities.

We note that a central aspect of the TPD component of this programme are weekly sessions. The sessions should not be blocked, e.g., to take place on a single day. Teachers must have time to teach between sessions; therefore, shorter weekly sessions should be organised instead of INSET days.

3.4.3. Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C4L2.1	Planning psychosocial and social support for teaching staff and instructors	Collaborate with the Ministry of Health to determine the nature of the support that will be provided, establish frequency and plan how it will be monitored.
C4L2.2	Establish support network for teachers	Establish a network for teachers to support each other, promote sharing good practice, provide emotional support and problem-solving. For example, such a network could consist of a set of WhatsApp groups, enabling teachers to reach out to each other.
C4L2.3	Implementing psychosocial / social support for teaching staff and instructors	Provision of counselling sessions or a counselling hotline to enable teachers to deal better with the crisis.
C4L2.4	TPD timescale and dissemination	Set up TPD timelines and disseminate TPD materials for schools to adapt as necessary. Each district should make decisions about when and how the sessions will take place (for example, after the school day, or during part of an abbreviated school day)
C4L2.5	Develop a monitoring and evaluation framework.	Set up a framework to review and monitor evaluation forms from TPD sessions. This will ensure that teachers are well supported in their growth.
C4L2.6	Follow-up visits	Undertake follow-up calls/visits based on information from the evaluation form.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.5. Diagnostic testing and student learning plans

Given the immense loss of learning resulting from unprecedented school closures during COVID-19, it is critical to know where students are in terms of learning outcomes to ensure that academic gaps are addressed. During meetings with teachers and stakeholders from the OECS territories, it was revealed that some students had not been reached with the blended learning efforts. This trend is no doubt similar to other parts of the region. Also, the current volcanic eruption in St Vincent exacerbated an already fragile situation. As emphasised by the **Let's REAP!**, diagnostic testing will enable teachers to gauge how much students know so that necessary interventions can be put in place to mitigate learning loss.

Critical pre-teaching and reteaching strategies have been suggested in the TPD to equip teachers to tackle unprecedented losses in academic outcomes. Also, sample tests have been included with the [Implementation Planning Tool](#), which will be available for teachers to modify and use should they wish to do so. Importantly, diagnostic tools provide resources and guidance to equip teachers to engage the most affected and most vulnerable students and their families.

3.5.1 Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C5L2.1	Monitoring of diagnostic test data	<p>Ensure that, from the earliest stages, diagnostic test data is sufficiently incorporated into monitoring frameworks.</p> <p>The MoE needs to review their respective national education monitoring frameworks and decide on key indicators (e.g., student attendance, student performance, teacher qualifications and capabilities, etc).</p>
C5L2.2	Record progress in diagnostic testing.	Record the total number of children in the school system, disaggregated by gender, when they have been assessed, and whether they are participating in the programme or not. Record the results in the sheet provided ('Participation', also see 'Participation — Guidance').
C5L2.3	Create a framework for analysis of diagnostic assessment	Develop a framework for teachers to submit and analyze results from diagnostic tests. Ideally, the framework should allow for comparison between test results at different times, comparison between groups of students and so on.
C5L2.4	Adapt CARICOM guidelines on formative assessment	Adapt CARICOM guidelines on formative assessment. The guidelines should include frequency of formative assessment and analysis of results.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.6. SPED, specialist teachers and educational psychologists / counsellors

While the budget for **Let's REAP!** implementation remains limited, the involvement of existing SPED staff and counsellors in TPD and training of teachers and instructors is crucial. Students with disabilities have been disproportionately affected by the pandemic, and additional attention should be given to evaluating their needs and providing support to ensure their achievement of key skills.

Counsellors are also key staff in identifying and addressing issues with students' psychosocial wellbeing. Where possible, counsellors should be involved in TPD training, and consideration should be given to the need for longer-term plans for hiring more counselling staff.

3.6.1. Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C6L2.1	Ensure robust M&E systems and identification processes	Put in place robust quality assurance monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure appropriate delivery. Ensure a national-level process for identifying SPED students is in place. This could involve implementing some digital tools.
C6L2.2	Clearly define the roles of stakeholders	Review and provide role clarity for teachers and other professionals so that they understand their responsibilities for ensuring the learning continuity of SPED students.
C6L2.3	Close technology and resource gaps	Take action to close the household-level technology gaps, particularly for SPED students. Determine how students with SPED can be supported with assistive technologies and ensure that such technologies are made available. Distribution of tablets, books and resources to SPED students as needed
C6L2.4	Provide resources to teachers and instructors	Provide resources and training for teachers to deliver distance education. Develop specific TPD sessions and resources for SPED teachers.
C6L2.5	Build partnerships with parents / caregivers	Build coalitions with parents or caregivers and non-government organisations to support continuity of learning for disadvantaged students.
C6L2.6	Work towards increased staffing	Develop plans to increase the number of school counsellors and educational psychologists. Determine appropriate long-term funds to support such staff.

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C6L2.7	Content sourcing for SPED	Sourcing and curation of content for SPED students
C6L2.8	Recruit and train more SPED teachers and instructors	Where budget allows, consider hiring of additional SPED instructors, teaching assistants and specialists. In addition, provide training for already existing SPED instructors.
C6L2.9	Collaborate with MoE on diagnosis	Determine whether MoMinistry of Health staff can support diagnosing SPED students.
C6L2.10	Collaborate with MoE on strategy	Work collaboratively with MoE to define / refine the SPED referral strategy.
C6L2.11	Contribute to designing of TPD	Support the design and delivery of SPED sessions (especially those linked with identifying disabilities).
C6L2.13	Awareness campaign rollout	<p>Work collaboratively with parents and schools to sensitise them about disabilities and reduce stigma.</p> <p>The awareness campaign could utilise TV, radio and newspapers. For example, radio clips could be produced and broadcast and 'advertisements' could be taken out in newspapers.</p>
C6L2.14	Adapt regional guidelines	Collaborate with MoE to adapt SPED guidelines provided by CARICOM and the OECS. SPED guidelines will inform the nature of services provided to students.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.7. Resources and curriculum

Accessing resources online is important. However, knowing how to acquire high-quality OER is critical to equipping teachers in middle-income countries like parts of the Caribbean region. The **Let's REAP!** implementation document guides the processes involved in working with OER material, including content curation and alignment, material development, content sourcing and review, and content inventory.

The key role of this section is to equip teachers to source and create content relevant to their classroom context and needs. In this way, it will save time and provide access to a range of high-quality content. Moreover, students may access OER at times, but teachers are guided to promote safeguarding practices for the well-being of their students.

3.7.1 Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C7L2.1	Content inventory	Carry out a content inventory of all the relevant content existing and identify content gaps.
C7L2.2	Content sourcing	Contribute to the CARICOM/OECS/CDB database of all readily available content (OER where possible).
C7L2.3	Review content	Review all the content collected on the basis of cultural relevance, quality and curriculum alignment.
C7L2.4	Content curation and alignment	Based on the review exercise, align content to the different subjects in the curriculum and upload it to a shared platform (such as the OECS ELP platform or Kolibri) which teachers and learners can access. Content should contain materials adapted for SPED students, as well as materials on pair tutoring, talk, and play.
C7.L2.5	Collate required inventory of resources	Compile a required inventory of all resources required by teachers, and review existing resources available to them
C7.L2.6	Ensure that teachers know how to use platform	Provide TPD sessions, tutorials and ongoing support to teachers on how to access these platforms

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.8. Support for parents and caregivers

Supporting parents and caregivers is critical to the success of the **Let's REAP!** implementation. Support requires several approaches to ensure that parents are equipped to assist their children at home effectively. It also includes checking in with parents to ascertain their psychosocial needs. Another critical aspect of this support is finding alternative ways to engage parents who are not offering full support to their child's education. This may involve finding out why they are not engaging.

3.8.1 Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C8L2.3	Update existing content for parents and develop new content as needed	Based on the findings in the first two stages, proceed to produce or repurpose content geared towards helping parents engage more actively in their children's education. Content should include pair mentoring with siblings / friends and the importance of talking and play activities.
C8L2.4	Roll out content	Make all content produced available to parents.
C8L2.5	Radio campaign	Create brief instructional radio scripts informing parents on best practice to support their child / children at home. Ideally, information should be brief and aired during prime time on a daily basis during a coordinated, intense campaign. Information should also be practical and relatable to the circumstances of a variety of parents. Involve parents in the design of these tools.
C8L2.6	Redefine counsellor roles	Revisit guidelines for the role of counsellors during the pandemic.
C8L2.7	Develop plan for increasing the number of counsellors	Consider finance and processes for hiring new counsellors.
C8L2.8	Adapt protocol for parental engagement	Adapt the protocol on parental engagement produced by CARICOM. Ensure that there are guidelines to engage parents who are reluctant to support their children and SPED students.

The above table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

3.9. Community organisations

Community organisations play critical roles in socialising the young. In addition, many students already receive some form of mentorship from participation in community groups and clubs. The **Let's REAP!** implementation tool provides guidance on recognising and effectively engaging, training, and monitoring collaborative work with community groups. A holistic approach that involves the Ministry of Education, schools and parents is recommended to effectively engage community groups where it is most needed in each school context.

The guide recognises that community groups are equipped with professionals who can assist in equipping students and their families to close academic gaps. In addition, community groups may be an essential resource for reaching parents who do not provide adequate support at home and who may not know how to help their children effectively.

3.9.1 Summary of actions for ministries in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C9L2.1	Identify community-based organisations and individuals	<p>Define parameters and specifications for the type of community-based organisations and individual profiles that can support the Let's REAP!. These may be community based-organisations and individuals who offer catch up lessons or remedial education to children. These may include faith-based groups, youth groups etc. These specifications should be shared with principals and school administrators</p> <p>Put in place a robust system or channel at the district level to collect, process and manage information on community-based organisations and individuals from teachers and principals</p> <p>The identification and evaluation process could be supported by local consultants who have access to community organisations. The evaluation could potentially be led by a community organisation, in collaboration with the community engagement teams put in place by principals.</p>
C9L2.2	Define shared goals / objectives	Explain the goals of the Let's REAP! to community figures and identify potential areas for collaboration
C9L2.3	Establish a role for appropriate individuals and organisations	Based on the findings in the first two steps, establish clearly defined roles and goals of the community organisations within the Let's REAP! context.

This table is an extract from the [↑Planning Tool](#).

4. Bibliography

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This bibliography is available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/FMVT2NIB>

Haßler, B., Adam, T., Blower, T., & Megha-Bongnkar, G. (2021b). *Academic Recovery Programmes in the Eastern Caribbean — Literature Review* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 1). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780577>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/DZA3GVBD>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Haßler, B., Blower, T., Megha-Bongnkar, G., & Regis, C. (2021c). *Academic Recovery Programme: Synthesis of Qualitative Data and High-level Overview* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 2). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780099>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/XAMQ949U>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021d). *An Academic Recovery Programme for the OECS for the OECS Member States* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 3). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780102>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/P2D5IJBC>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021e). *An Academic Recovery Programme for the OECS for the OECS Member States: Pitch Deck* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 4). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780107>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/XQCXWE7I>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021fa). *Implementation Planning Tool* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Implementation Planning Tool No. 1). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4779907>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/EM6IJ327>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Haßler, B., Megha-Bongnkar, G., Regis, C., & Blower, T. (2021g). *Final Report and Recommendations* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 6). Open

4. Bibliography

Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603101>. Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/TD6VRUSA>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Acknowledgements

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